

PROBLEMS OF INTERRELATION BETWEEN LANGUAGE AND THINKING

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Abstract. *In this article, problems of interrelation between language and thinking are given on the point of view of the author. According to the author language is often characterized as a tool, an instrument of thinking, and the relationship between language and thinking as their unity. The author highlights the key facts in this sphere.*

Key words: *brain, complexity, communication, human, language, logical, philosophy, relationship, social, thinking.*

Annotasiya. *Ushbu maqolada til va tafakkur o'rtasidagi o'zaro bog'liqlik muammolari muallif nuqtai nazaridan berilgan. Muallifning fikricha, til ko'pincha tafakkur quroli, quroli, til va tafakkur o'rtasidagi munosabat esa ularning birligi sifatida tavsiflanadi. Muallif ushbu sohadagi asosiy faktlarni ta'kidlaydi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *miya, murakkablik, muloqot, inson, til, mantiq, falsafa, munosabatlar, ijtimoiy, tafakkur.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье проблемы взаимосвязи языка и мышления изложены с точки зрения автора. По мнению автора, язык часто характеризуется как орудие, инструмент мышления, а взаимоотношения языка и мышления — как их единство. Автор выделяет ключевые факты в этой сфере.*

Ключевые слова: *мозг, сложность, коммуникация, человек, язык, логический, философия, отношения, социальный, мышление.*

Interest in language as a means of communication arose in the late 19th century in the wake of criticism of positivism and neo-Hegelianism. Scientists and philosophers such as Bertrand Russell, Ludwig Wittgenstein, and Rudolf Carnap argued that pure and objective knowledge cannot be obtained through the senses and observation, because the main tool, language, is not an accurate and precise means of transmitting information. Based on this criticism, such philosophical movements as neo positivism, analytical philosophy, and the logic of science emerged – their goal was to recognize the inaccuracies of language and eliminate its imperfections. The problem of the relationship between language and thinking is one of the most complex and pressing issues not only in general linguistics, but also in logic, psychology, and philosophy. There is probably not a single significant work in the field of these sciences throughout their entire development that would not discuss or at least raise this issue in one form or another. The complexity of the problem is primarily due to the complexity and contradictory nature of both thinking and language. Being necessary attributes of man, both phenomena combine the social and the biological (in accordance with the dual nature of man). On the one hand, both language and thinking are products of the human brain as homo sapiens, on the other hand, language and thinking are social products, since man himself is a social phenomenon.

One of the first scientific questions that brought together different areas of research (the study of language and the study of thinking): can a person think without the help of language? Does our language control our thoughts? After the close relationship between language and

thinking was revealed, this problem became very popular among cognitive sciences. Most researchers adhere to one of three statements: thinking exists on the basis of language; language and thinking are identical; thinking is a more complex mental reflex than language. According to A. A. Abramyan "the individual is a social being. Therefore, every manifestation of his life - even if it does not appear in the direct form of a collective manifestation of life, carried out together with others - is a manifestation and affirmation of social life" [Abramyan, 1965:174]. In the unity of the social and the individual-biological, the most general specificity of both language and thinking is manifested. It is this, apparently, that primarily explains the difficult to discern diversity of concepts that existed and exist in the relevant sciences regarding both language and thinking, and thus the relationship between them. At the same time, it is important to emphasize the determinacy of these concepts by certain philosophical systems, which were sometimes even unconsciously shared by their authors. The solution to the problem of the relationship between language and thought (the relationship between word and thought) "has always and constantly fluctuated – from the most ancient times to the present day – between two extreme poles – between the identification and complete fusion of thought and word and between their equally metaphysical, equally absolute, equally complete rupture and separation" [Admoni, 1965:46].

The identification of language and thought (it should be noted that it does not always occur in an explicit form) logically leads to the removal of the problem altogether. The question of the connection between language and thought is declared a pseudo-problem and is eliminated from the researcher's field of vision. The complete separation and opposition of language and thought as independent and only externally related phenomena, the consideration of the word as an external expression of thought, its clothing - "only cuts the knot, instead of untying it", because in this case the connection is considered as something so mechanical that it can be neglected when considering both related phenomena [Admoni, 1961: 78]. At present, both extreme tendencies continue to exist in various forms.

Thus, different attitudes to thinking and its connection with language underlie two different directions: "mentalis tic", which notes the desire to identify language and thinking, to attribute to language the role in the human psyche that belongs to thinking, and "mechanistic" (behaviorist), which separates language from thought, considering thinking as something extra linguistic (extra linguistic) and excluding it from the theory of language, to the point that thinking is generally declared a fiction [Berg, 1965: 103]. Apparently, the correct approach to this problem will be the one that proceeds from the obvious fact - the presence of a complex relationship between language and thinking. In general, it is presented as follows. The basis of the content expressed in language is formed by thoughts. It is through thinking, through the reflective activity of the human brain, that linguistic units can correlate with objects and phenomena of the objective world, without which communication between people using language would be impossible. "On the other hand, in the sound complexes of a language, which act as material signals of the elements of the objective world reflected in thinking, the results of cognition are fixed, and these results serve as the basis for further cognition" [Vygotsky, 1934:124]. However, this postulate alone does not solve the entire problem. The relationship between language and thought (consciousness) is part of a broader problem - the problem of the relationship of three links: language - thinking - objective reality, or, as this problem is often formulated, words - thoughts - things.

In terms of the main question of philosophy, the relationship of thinking (consciousness) to objective reality comes to the fore in this triad, which in turn determines the relationship of language to things. We were all taught to read in roughly the same way: first we memorized

letters, then we were taught to form syllables, then words, and finally, to read sentences. This is a standard elementary school technique that determines how we learn to read. The hidden side of this process is that many begin to identify what is written with the image that is formed in the head (this is related to the field of neurolinguistics). The secret of people who read quickly is that they have better developed peripheral vision, they concentrate less on the level of signs, letters, and they do not pronounce the word in their heads, they do not have sub vocalization. Thanks to speech, people communicate with each other, convey their thoughts, knowledge, express feelings and desires.

Thus, thinking cannot proceed independently of speech, language, it is impossible to formulate thoughts without linguistic material. They immediately mentally recognize the image. Language and thinking are inextricably linked as types of social activity. Language forms a unity with thinking, since without thinking there can be no language and thinking without language is impossible. However, it should be immediately noted that thinking can be both verbal and non-verbal (visual-figurative). Thinking allows us to connect the elements of consciousness into a single whole, language and speech allow us to clarify and clarify consciousness. Consciousness acquires order and clarity only through thinking. Therefore, the connection between these concepts is unusually strong. Another study suggests that the more languages we learn (especially in childhood), the easier it is for our brains to process and remember new information. It appears that learning a language helps form new neural connections in the brain. Verbal-logical thinking is a complex higher form of thinking, and therefore its development must be approached in a comprehensive manner, not forgetting about each mental operation.

Conclusion: Language is a symbolic activity that provides the material design of thoughts and the exchange of information between members of society. Thinking, with the exception of its practical-active form, has a psychic, ideal nature, while language is a phenomenon that is primarily physical and material in nature. Language and thinking have been of interest to scientists for over 150 years. But, as recent discoveries show, we are only at the threshold of understanding how these complex psychological phenomena interact in our brain. According to linguist modern linguists we do not have reliable information to talk about the dominance of one reflex over another. Despite this outcome, in real life we have many examples not only of how language can be a means of influence and achieving one's own goals, but also of how critical thinking can resist the influence of language. No matter how complex and unexplored the field of human existence our brain is, we can learn to consciously control both language and thinking. The only question is for what purpose this should be done. Language and thinking are two inextricably linked types of social activity that differ from each other in their essence and specific features. Thinking is the highest form of active reflection of objective reality, purposeful, mediated and generalized knowledge of the essential connections and relationships of objects and phenomena. Language is a sign (in its original form, sound) activity that ensures the material design of thoughts and the exchange of information between members of society.

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